

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Health
OFFICE OF THE SECRETARY

June 21 / 21
~~March 23~~, 2018

ADMINISTRATIVE ORDER
No. 2018 - 0007-A

SUBJECT: Amendment to Administrative Order (AO). No. 2018-0007 entitled "Interim Guidelines on Investigating Deaths related to Dengvaxia Immunization"

On March 9, 2018 an orientation on the standard procedures in autopsy was conducted by an expert from the UP-PGH DITF and was attended by the autopsy teams from the respective DOH Reference Hospitals. During the said orientation, several issues and clarifications were raised by the participants necessary for the proper implementation of the autopsy procedures.

Pursuant to A.O. No. 2018-0007 entitled "Interim Guidelines on Investigating Deaths related to Dengvaxia Immunization" the following provisions and specific Annexes are hereby amended:

V. GENERAL GUIDELINES

-XXX-

Under Nos. 02 and 03

2. All medical documents of Dengvaxia-related deaths shall be submitted to UP-PGH DITF within 24 hours after death, for assessment of causality.
3. All Dengvaxia related deaths shall be advised for autopsy, including those who have already been buried, provided the required consent of the next of kin of the deceased, and the local health officer were obtained, accordingly.

The aforementioned is hereby amended to include no. 02 and to read as follows:

2. **To verify if the deceased received Dengvaxia vaccine, ensure that the deceased has the Dengue Identification Card (ID) issued by the Department of Health (DOH). This may be verified thru the following DOH Dengue hotline:**

a. DOH Central Office

☎ (02)711-1001, (02) 711-1002

☎ 0920-110-7498, 0915-772-5621

b. Regional Office III

☎ (045) 455-2322

c. Regional Office IV-A

☎ (02) 440-3372

☎ 0927-580-5551

d. Regional Office VII

☎ (032) 418-7010

☎ 0922-397-2334

3. All medical documents of Dengvaxia-related deaths shall be submitted to UP-PGH DITF within 24 hours after death, for assessment of causality **through their respective Regional Offices (ROs)**.
4. All Dengvaxia related deaths shall be advised for autopsy, including those who have already been buried, provided the required consent of the next of kin of the deceased, and the local health officer were obtained, accordingly. **However, to prevent exposure of hospital personnel to any potential risk, the autopsy procedure must not be performed if the deceased is highly suspected to have acquired any of the following dangerous communicable diseases (as enumerated on PD 856 Code on Sanitation of the Philippines and Administrative Order 2010-0033 Revised Implementing Rules and Regulations of PD 856 Code of Sanitation of the Philippines Chapter XXI “Disposal of Dead Persons”):**
 - a. **Hepatitis B and C**
 - b. **Rabies**
 - c. **Invasive group A streptococcal infections**
 - d. **Transmissible spongiform encephalopathies (e.g. Creutzfeldt- Jakob disease with necropsy, mad cow disease)**
 - e. **HIV/AIDS**
 - f. **Meningococemia**
 - g. **Viral hemorrhagic fevers (e.g. African Ebolas, Lassa or Marburg)**
 - h. **Yellow fever**
 - i. **Plague**
 - j. **Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS)**
 - k. **Other communicable diseases that shall be declared by the Department**

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VI. SPECIFIC GUIDELINES

Under No. 1, 2e (inclusion), 3d, 3e, 3f (inclusion), 8a, 9c, 10a and 10b

1. Submission of Clinical Records to UP-PGH DITF:

All public and private hospitals are required to submit within 24 hours to UP-PGH DITF the complete clinical records of the deaths related to Dengvaxia vaccines, for assessment.

3. Institutions / Persons Authorized to Perform Autopsy:

- d. For deaths occurring in hospitals not identified as DOH Reference Hospitals or deaths in private hospitals, the designated Autopsy Team shall conduct the autopsy in the nearest government hospital, or in the National Bureau of Investigation (NBI) - accredited morgue (Annex B), within the locality.
- e. The Autopsy Team shall be composed of the following from the DOH Reference Hospital:
 - i. One (1) Anatomical Pathologist
 - ii. Two (2) Mortician trained in evisceration

DOH may invite a foreign pathology expert as resource person in the Autopsy Team, if deemed necessary.

8. Requirements for Exhumation

- a. The disinterment or exhumation permit shall be issued by the local health officer and all disinterment of remains shall be under their supervision.

9. Risk Communication to Bereaved Family:

- c. Any proprietary or confidential information obtained during the autopsy shall not be disclosed without prior consent or clearance from DOH.

10. Referral Facilities Authorized to Conduct Autopsy

- a. All DOH Reference Hospitals in Regions III, IV-A, NCR and VII will conduct autopsy.
- b. If patient died in a lower level facility or at home, the autopsy may be conducted by the autopsy team in a NBI-accredited morgue.

The aforementioned is hereby amended to read as follows:

1. Submission of Clinical Records to UP-PGH DITF:

All public and private hospitals are required to submit within 24 hours to UP-PGH DITF **through their ROs** the complete clinical records of the deaths related to Dengvaxia vaccines, for assessment, **provided that consent for the release of medical records and information necessary for the investigation deaths in English (Annex E) and Filipino (Annex F) shall be secured from the next of kin.**

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NW M J

2. Consent before the Conduct of Autopsy

- e. **The Autopsy consent form is in English (Annex G) and Filipino (Annex H). The DOH Reference Hospitals may translate the said consent form into their respective dialects.**

3. Institutions / Persons Authorized to Perform Autopsy:

- d. For deaths occurring in hospitals not identified as DOH Reference Hospitals or deaths in private hospitals, the designated Autopsy Team shall conduct the autopsy in the nearest government hospital within the locality.

- e. The Autopsy Team shall be composed of the following from the DOH Reference Hospital:

- i. One (1) Anatomic Pathologist
- ii. **One (1) Morgue technician or any designated hospital personnel provided that he/she shall be trained by the hospital Anatomic Pathologist**
- iii. **Health Education and Promotion Officer (HEPO)**
- iv. **Other specialist(s)/subspecialist(s), if necessary, which may include but is not limited to a/an:**
 - 1. **Pediatrician**
 - 2. **Internist**
 - 3. **Infectious Disease specialist**

The DOH may also invite a foreign pathology expert as resource person in the Autopsy Team, if deemed necessary.

- f. **Universal precautions are the basic standard of infection control. Hence, all authorized/permitted personnel present during the conduct of autopsy must wear complete Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) which includes: gloves, mask, eye protection/goggles, scrub/ gowns/aprons, rubber boots among others.**

8. Requirements for Exhumation

- a. **The disinterment or exhumation permit shall be issued by the local health officer once approval of the respective DOH Regional Directors has been granted. The disinterment of remains shall be under the supervision of the local health officer. Refer to Annex D on the Exhumation Indorsement Form.**

9. Risk Communication to Bereaved Family:

- c. **Information to be given to the families should only be the initial findings based on the autopsy report. It should be emphasized that these findings are still inconclusive as it needs to be correlated with the causality assessment done by UP PGH DITF. Any other**

proprietary or confidential information obtained during the autopsy shall not be disclosed without prior consent or clearance from DOH.

10. Referral Facilities Authorized to Conduct Autopsy

- a. All DOH Reference Hospitals in Regions III, IV-A, NCR and VII will conduct autopsy. **The identification of Reference Hospitals per region does not limit the Regional Offices/ Reference Hospitals to seek the assistance from other DOH Reference Hospitals and their respective Autopsy teams in the conduct of autopsy.**
- b. If patient died in a lower level facility or at home, the autopsy may be conducted by the autopsy team in **the nearest government hospital.**

-XXX-

Annex A DOH Reference Hospitals – Region III:

Name	Location
Region III	
1. Dr. Paulino J. Garcia Memorial Research and Medical Center	Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija
2. Jose B. Lingad Memorial Regional Hospital	San Fernando, Pampanga

~~Annex B - NBI Accredited Morgue:~~

The aforementioned is hereby amended to include Bataan General Hospital as a DOH Reference Hospital in Region III and to read as follows:

Name	Location
Region III	
4. Dr. Paulino J. Garcia Memorial Research and Medical Center	Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija
2. Jose B. Lingad Memorial Regional Hospital	San Fernando, Pampanga
3. Bataan General Hospital	Balanga, Bataan

And to exclude Annex B NBI Accredited Morgue to be replaced by Autopsy Report Guide

-XXX-

All other provisions of AO 2018-0007 shall remain in effect and provisions/issuances inconsistent or contrary to this Order are hereby rescinded or modified accordingly.

This order shall take effect immediately.

FRANCISCO T. DUQUE III, MD, MSc
 Secretary of Health

ANNEX B

AUTOPSY REPORT GUIDE

- I. Secure consent for autopsy (DOH Autopsy Form No. 1) from next of kin.
- II. Review **clinical history/historical summary** (includes patient's medical history, laboratory and imaging findings) and discuss with the attending physician(s).
 - a. Secure pre-mortem blood and other body fluid samples from the laboratory (if available) and store them following DOH AO2018-000
- III. Prior to performing external examination of the body, **VERIFY** that the name on the consent matches the body/name tag attached the corpse prior to any incision. Verify identifying markers carefully. The birth date can be a useful cross-check for correct patient identification.
- IV. Universal precaution **MUST** be observed at all times. PPE (as a last resort in providing a barrier to the hazard)
 - a. Gloves for handling all potentially contaminated materials, containers, equipment, or surfaces.
 - b. Face protection (face shields, splash goggles worn with masks, masks with built-in eye shield).
 - c. Laboratory coats and gowns to prevent exposure of street clothing, and gloves or bandages to protect nonintact skin.
 - d. Additional respiratory protection if warranted by risk assessment.

Demographic Data Checklist:

1. Include the name and address of the institution on the autopsy report
2. Identify the patient by name, hospital number.
3. Provide the patient's date of birth
4. Assign a unique autopsy number for each case.
5. The final admission date, obtained from hospital records, allows calculation of the duration of hospital stay.
6. Include the date and time of death
7. State the place of death, ward, hospital service, or other source of the autopsy case, as appropriate.
8. State the date and time of autopsy.
9. State the extent of autopsy, including restrictions. An unrestricted autopsy should be described as such. Permissions and restrictions given by the responsible party should be listed.
10. The prosector's name should be included. The prosector is defined as the person who dissects the organs. This individual may be the same person as the attending pathologist, in which case the name should be listed redundantly.
11. Include other necessary information like the patient's address, as well as the

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patient's usual occupation.

12. A listing of ancillary studies (eg, microbiology, toxicology, serology, photomicrography, and electron microscopy), and the patient's physicians of record may be included on the report.

V. Perform **external examination** of the body

- a. Document findings using notes, drawings and photographs.
- b. Include pertinent negatives.
- c. Include body height, weight, nutrition, eyes (irides, sclera, and conjunctiva), nose, ears, mouth, teeth, neck, chest, abdomen, genitalia, and extremities.
- d. For all pediatric autopsies, include head, abdominal and chest circumference.

VI. **Evisceration and Internal Examination** (all internal organs should be inspected, weighed and described)

- a. Eviscerate the body using the standard Y-shaped incision.
- b. After removal of the sternal plate, collect the following specimens:
 - Blood – approximately 5 – 10 cc.
 1. Central (or heart blood)
 2. Peripheral (or iliac/femoral blood)
 - Urine - approximately 5 – 10 cc.
 - Vitreous humor (mandatory especially for embalmed and decomposing remains) – collect as much fluid as possible from both eyes; a single syringe may be used to obtain and keep the fluid from both eyes.
 - Stomach contents (only if oral poisoning is being considered)

- Cerebrospinal fluid and other swabs (if microbial studies are needed)
- For collection of body fluid, use clean syringe for each body cavity.

- c. Proceed with removal of the organ bloc.
- d. Dissect the organ bloc, documenting all findings by notation and photography.
- Weigh each major organ.
 - The external and cut surfaces of all major organs should be described in terms of color, appearance and consistency. Dissect thoroughly.
 - All positive findings should be described in terms of measurement, color, appearance and consistency. Measurements should be in centimeters (cm).
 - Take photos of whole and sectioned organs together with label and ruler.
 - Pertinent negatives should also be listed based on the peculiarities of the case.

- Body cavities
 - Organ arrangement
 - General appearance of viscera (degree of decomposition, color)
 - Adipose layer of anterior abdominal body wall
- Central Nervous System
 - Weight of brain
 - Configuration of brain
 - Meninges
 - Abnormalities evident externally (hemorrhage, herniations, infection, etc)
 - Blood vessels
 - Internal abnormalities
 - Ventricular system
 - Pituitary gland
 - Scalp and skull
- Neck
 - General appearance
 - Trachea
 - Lymph nodes
 - Airway
 - Blood vessels
 - Other abnormalities noted:
- Cardiovascular system
 - Heart (g):
 - Dominance (L/R):
 - Configuration
 - Coronary arteries
 - Right coronary artery:
 - Left anterior descending artery:
 - Left circumflex artery:
 - Valves (including circumferences, if abnormal)
 - Tricuspid Valve:
 - Mitral Valve:

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For limited autopsy, liver and spleen should at least be included.		Ethanol (1:1 ratio).		
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- For fresh tissues

Two sets of tissues shall be collected – one set collected and stored fresh as detailed below and a second set collected and stored as formalinized tissues as detailed above.

<p>Post-mortem tissues from all major organs should be submitted for evaluation. Specimens should include:</p> <p>a. Heart (right ventricle, septum, and left ventricle)</p> <p>b. CNS (cerebral cortex, thalamus, basal ganglia, midbrain, pons, medulla, cerebellum, and spinal cord)</p> <p>Representative sections from the ff:</p> <p>a. Right & left lungs</p> <p>b. Right & left kidneys</p> <p>c. Spleen</p> <p>d. Liver</p> <p>e. Bone marrow</p> <p>f. Lymph nodes</p> <p>g. Any other organ showing significant gross pathology</p> <p>h. Effusion: pleural and pericardial fluids</p> <p>For limited autopsy, liver and spleen should at least be included.</p>	<p>Collect specimen FRESH, as soon as possible after death.</p>	<p>At least three (3) pieces from each organ, each piece measuring at least 2.0 cm.</p> <p>All specimens (including effusion fluid) should be collected aseptically. Use a separate sterile instrument for each collection site.</p> <p>Place each specimen in sterile wide-mouthed container / jar (Label should include patient's name, specimen type, laterality, date and time collected).</p> <p>At least 5 to 10 ml without any fixative.</p>	<p>Frozen at -20°C prior to shipping. If biofreezer is unavailable, store at 2 to 8 °C in a standard refrigerator.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport immediately in a well-sealed container. • Use the prescribed transport box with gel or ice packs • Avoid repetitive freezing and thawing of specimens.
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- VII. **Trim sections for microscopic examination.**
VIII. **Perform microscopic examination.**
IX. **Prepare autopsy report which should include the following:**
- a. Case identifiers
 - b. Gross description
 - External examination
 - Internal examination
 - c. Microscopic description
 - **Make a key or summary noting block and slide designations.
 - d. Ancillary studies (include any reports of microbiological, chemical, histochemical, toxicologic and immunologic analyses; electron microscopy; cytogenetic studies; or of any other studies performed on materials from the autopsy).
 - e. Anatomic diagnosis
 - f. Summary and interpretation which should include:
 - Brief clinical summary including pertinent laboratory and radiologic findings
 - A clinicopathologic summary providing an objective correlation of clinical findings with gross and microscopic findings and the results of other studies performed at autopsy to describe the death and to elucidate the sequence of events leading to death.
 - Cause of death statement which must include the immediate and/or intermediate and/or underlying cause of death
 - g. The autopsy release date or autopsy completion date.

SOME KEY POINTERS:

Ancillary Studies

1. If copies of photographs or radiographs are available but are not included in the protocol, make a note of their existence, location, and content.

Clinical History

1. Clinical history may be a part of the autopsy report, but it should be no more than a summary of factual material contained in the patient chart.

Communication: Completion and Distribution of Reports

1. If the autopsy diagnoses and findings are provisional, that fact should be indicated on the face sheet.

** There will be occasions when the pathologist determines that an autopsy should not be released until further information is received, even when this lengthens the turnaround time of the autopsy. For example, the pathologist may decide that the cause of death cannot be determined without a full evaluation of neuropathology and special

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studies of brain slides. The pathologist might decide that it would be pointless and misleading to release the autopsy while these studies are still pending. In such cases, the pathologist should not feel obligated to release the autopsy. On the other hand, if the cause of death is apparent, the pathologist might release the autopsy report rapidly and add the results of pending studies as supplemental reports as they become available.

X. **Submit** autopsy report to PGH DITF.

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ANNEX D

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Health

EXHUMATION FORM FOR DENG VAXIA VACCINEES

1st Indorsement

Date of indorsement

Respectfully forwarded to _____, Local Health Officer,
(Name of Local Health Officer)
 _____ Health Department, _____ hereby approving
(Location of City Health) *(Municipality/City)*
 the attached request of _____ to disinter / exhume the remains of
(Name of Requesting Party)
 _____, buried at _____ City Cemetery, for the
(Name of Decent/Patient) *(Location of Burial)*
 autopsy of the remains and its eventual re-interment to the same cemetery pursuant to Chapter XXI "Disposal of Dead Persons" of the Code on Sanitation of the Philippines (PD 856), provided such disinter / exhumation should be done under the direct supervision of your office.

NAME OF DOH REGIONAL DIRECTOR
 Position
 Regional Director

Attachments:

- Request Letter for Exhumation
- Death Certificate
- Indorsement Letter to DOH regional Director from Local Health Office

Amount Paid : _____
 Official Receipt No. : _____
 Date Issued : _____

[Handwritten Signature]
 Page 14 of 26
[Handwritten Signature]

ANNEX E

CONSENT FOR RELEASE OF MEDICAL RECORDS AND INFORMATION NECESSARY FOR THE INVESTIGATION DEATHS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES – PHILIPPINE GENERAL HOSPITAL DENGUE INVESTIGATIVE TASK FORCE (UP-PGH DITF)

Form with fields: NAME OF DECEDENT/PATIENT, DATE OF BIRTH, DATE/TIME OF DEATH, NAME AND TITLE OF PHYSICIAN PERFORMING PROCEDURE, LICENSE NUMBER, NAME OF FACILITY WHERE THE PROCEDURE WILL BE PERFORMED.

I, (Full Name) _____ bearing the relationship of (in order of legal consent) [please check whichever is applicable] parent siblings (18 years old and older) grandparent guardian (at time of death) to the deceased hereby authorize the hospital/ attending physician to release the deceased’s medical records and information to the University of the Philippines – Philippine General Hospital Dengue Investigative Task Force (UP-PGH DITF) and the Department of Health (DOH).

The records or information obtained from the (hospital or the attending physician) shall be for the purpose of further investigation. I understand that these records shall be used to fully understand the cause of death and the effects of treatment and for diagnostic, education and research purposes.

This consent includes the release of information such as clinical abstract, laboratory results, doctor’s order, medication sheet, and discharge summary as deemed necessary by the hospital and/or UP-PGH DITF.

CONSENTEE (NEXT OF KIN):

EXPLAINED BY (AUTOPSY TEAM):

Signature: _____
Complete Name: _____
Date (mm/dd/yyyy): _____

Signature: _____
Name & position: _____
Date (mm/dd/yyyy): _____

WITNESS:

Signature: _____
Name & position: _____
Date (mm/dd/yyyy): _____

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ANNEX F

**PAHINTULOT PARA SA PAGPAPALABAS NG MEDIKAL NA TALA AT
IMPORMASYON NA KINAKAILANGAN PARA SA IMBESTIGASYON NG
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES – PHILIPPINE GENERAL HOSPITAL DENGUE
INVESTIGATIVE TASK FORCE (UP-PGH DITF)**

PANGALAN NG NAMATAY/PASYENTE: <i>(Unang Pangalan, Gitnang Pangalan, Apelyido)</i>	PETSA NG KAPANGANAKAN: <i>(Buwan/Araw/Taon)</i>	PETSA/ORAS NG KAMATAYAN: <i>(Buwan/Araw/Taon) (12-hr format)</i>
PANGALAN AT TITULO NG DOKTOR NA MAGSASAGAWA NG AUTOPSYA:		BILANG NG LISENSYA:
PANGALAN NG PASILIDAD KUNG SAAN ISASAGAWA ANG AUTOPSIYA:		

Ako, (Buong Pangalan) _____ na (ayon sa karapatang legal) [lagyan ng tsek ang alin mang naaangkop] magulang kapatid (18 taong gulang pataas) lolo/lola tagapangalaga (sa panahon ng pagkamatay) ng namatay, na binigyang-karapatan ng batas na magpasya *ay nagbibigay pahintulot sa* ospital at/o ang nakatalagang manggagamot na ipalabas ang mga medikal na tala at impormasyon sa University of the Philippines – Philippine General Hospital Dengue Investigative Task Force (UP-PGH DITF) at sa Kagawaran ng Kalusugan.

Ang mga nakuhang mga talaang medikal o anumang impormasyon mula sa ospital o sa nakatalagang manggagamot ay gagamitin para sa layunin ng higit na pagsisiyasat. Nauunawaan ko na ang mga talaang medikal ay gagamitin upang lubos na maunawaan ang sanhi ng pagkamatay at ang mga epekto ng panggagamot para sa mga layuning dayagnostiko, pang-edukasyon at pananaliksik.

Kabilang sa pahintulot na ito ang pagbibigay impormasyon tulad ng *clinical abstract*, resulta mula sa laboratoryo, *doctor's order*, *medication sheet* at discharge summary ayon sa pangangailangan ng ospital at/o ng UP-PGH DITF.

**NAGBIBIGAY NG PAHINTUHOT IPINALIWANAG NI (AUTOPSY
(PINAKAMALAPIT NA KAMAGANAK): TEAM):**

Lagda: _____ Lagda ng Saksi: _____
Buong Pangalan: _____ Pangalan at Posisyon: _____
Petsa (Buwan/Araw/Taon): _____ Petsa (Buwan/Araw/Taon): _____

SAKSI:

Lagda ng Saksi: _____
Pangalan at Posisyon: _____
Petsa (Buwan/Araw/Taon): _____

ANNEX G

**AUTOPSY CONSENT FORM
FOR DENGVAXIA VACCINEES**

NAME OF DECEDENT/PATIENT: <i>(First Name, Middle Name, Surname)</i>	DATE OF BIRTH: <i>(Month/Date/Year)</i>	DATE/TIME OF DEATH: <i>(Month/Date/Year)(12-hr format)</i>
NAME AND TITLE OF PHYSICIAN PERFORMING PROCEDURE:		LICENSE NUMBER:
NAME OF FACILITY WHERE THE PROCEDURE WILL BE PERFORMED:		

Please read the reverse before completing the form

I, (Full Name) _____ bearing the relationship of (in order of legal consent) [please check whichever is applicable] parent siblings (18 years old and older) grandparent guardian (at time of death) to the deceased having the right under the law to have control on the disposition of the deceased body/remains, hereby authorize the pathologist of the Department of Health Reference Hospital/ DOH Autopsy Team to perform an autopsy.

I declare that, to the best of my knowledge, no individual of higher order of legal consent would object to the performance of the autopsy to the deceased's body/remains.

If there is more than one person of the same relation entitled to give consent to a postmortem examination or autopsy, consent may be given by a member of the same relationship unless another person of the same relationship files an objection with the physician, medical examiner, justice or judge of the regular courts of justice. If an objection is filed, the consent may be given only by a majority of the persons of the same relationship of the class who are reasonably available. An example of this would be multiple surviving adult children.

By signing, I authorize the removal, examination, and retention of organs, tissues, prosthetic and implantable devices, and fluids as the pathologists deem proper for further investigation to fully understand the cause of death and the effects of treatment, for diagnostic, education and research purposes.

I consent that photographs and other forms of documentation may be taken as part of the autopsy process, provided that the photographs will not identify the deceased by name, face, or other identifying physical features. I also understand that any photos taken and other forms of documentation will not be publicly displayed nor will be used for any other purposes other than those above-mentioned.

I understand that it will be necessary for small pieces of tissue (diagnostic samples) to be sent for laboratory testing. This is essential for a complete, informative autopsy. I understand that organs and tissues not needed for diagnostic, education, quality improvement, or research purposes will

be sent to the funeral home or disposed of appropriately. Further, I agree to the eventual disposition of these materials as determined by the pathologists or the hospital or as required by law.

I consent the use of the deceased's medical record and all other relevant information obtained from the hospital (or the attending physician) for the purpose of further investigation. I understand that these records shall be used to fully understand the cause of death and the effects of treatment and for diagnostic, education and research purposed.

I understand that any diagnostic information gained from the autopsy will become part of the deceased's medical record and will be submitted to the University of the Philippines – Philippine General Hospital Dengue Investigative Task Force (UP-PGH DITF) for further analysis subject to applicable law.

This consent does not extend to the removal or use of any of these materials for transplantation or similar purposes.

I understand that I may place limitations on both the extent of the autopsy and on the retention of organs, tissue, and devices. I understand that any limitations may compromise the diagnostic value of the autopsy and may limit the usefulness of the autopsy for education, quality improvement, or research purpose

Autopsy restrictions (choose only one option)

- None. Permission is granted for a **complete autopsy**, with removal, examination and retention of materials as the pathologists deem proper for the purposes set forth above, and for disposition of such material as the pathologists or the hospital determine.

Limit the Autopsy to

- Partial Autopsy (Thoracoabdominal Area only)

___ Exam is restricted to the liver only

___ Exam is restricted to the liver, chest cavity

___ Exam is restricted to the liver and abdominal cavity

___ Exam is restricted to the liver, chest and abdominal cavity only

___ Other: (Specify) _____

- Limited Autopsy: Getting slabs of tissue/ or using aspiration technique on specific organ of the body. Kindly indicate the organ(s) _____

I have read and understood the Autopsy Information for the Family (next page).

I was informed of my right to have a physician of my choice to be present as observer during the conduct of the autopsy. (Please check only one option, and fill out the blank, if necessary):

- I waive my right to have a physician of my choice to be present as observer during the conduct autopsy

I have a physician of my choice to be present as observer during the conduct of autopsy, in the person of:

Complete Name and License Number of the Physician

I have been given the opportunity to ask any questions that I may have regarding the scope or purpose of the autopsy.

CONSENTEE (NEXT OF KIN):

Signature: _____
Complete Name: _____
Date (mm/dd/yyyy): _____

EXPLAINED BY (AUTOPSY TEAM):

Signature: _____
Name & position: _____
Date (mm/dd/yyyy): _____

WITNESS:

Signature: _____
Name & position: _____
Date (mm/dd/yyyy): _____

AUTOPSY – INFORMATION FOR THE FAMILY

What is an autopsy?

A physician who specializes in pathology (a pathologist), will perform an examination of a body after death to determine the cause of death or the character and extent of changes produced by disease. This includes the external and internal examination of the body and its organs and supplemented by microscopic examination when necessary.

Why is it performed?

An autopsy can confirm or determine the cause of death, and identify the nature and extent of any other diseases present. It may also help you better understand the deceased's illness and cause of death. It may provide information that may be relevant to you and other relatives' health conditions.

General Information

- ❖ You are able to decide whether the deceased will have a complete or a limited hospital autopsy. It is important that you understand and are comfortable with what you are asked to authorize.
- ❖ During a complete autopsy, a pathologist undertakes an external and internal examination of the body. To allow this to happen, the internal organs are removed from the chest, abdomen, and head and are examined.
- ❖ In a limited autopsy, the examination is restricted to only particular regions or organs of the body that you agree to. However, a limited hospital autopsy may not provide all the information necessary to determine what caused or contributed to the death.
- ❖ Removing and keeping diagnostic samples is a usual part of most autopsies. These samples may be examined by the pathologist using a microscope.
- ❖ Most organs and tissues are returned to the body at the end of the hospital autopsy unless you give specific permission for an organ or organs to be retained for further examination. Certain medical conditions (such as diseases of the brain), may require retaining the entire organ. Allowing the pathologist discretion in this matter ensures maximum possible information in the final autopsy report.
- ❖ At the completion of the examination, these organs and any samples that remain after testing will be:
 - disposed of respectfully by the hospital, or
 - at your request, released to a funeral director for burial or cremation at a later date, (may incur additional funeral costs to the family), or
 - at your request, all samples are returned to the body before the funeral (may also incur additional funeral costs to the family)
- ❖ You can consent to diagnostic samples and/or extra tissue being removed for purposes of research, teaching and future laboratory use. Separate authorization will be sought for your consent for the use of samples or tissues in specific research projects.

What happens after the autopsy?

The organs are returned to the body and the body is closed with great care and respect so that it is always possible for a viewing after the hospital autopsy.

Will the autopsy team delay the funeral?

The funeral will only be delayed if you decide that all of the diagnostic samples must be returned prior to the funeral.

How will the family know the outcome of the autopsy?

The detailed autopsy report will be completed by the pathologist. The report will then be sent to the UP-PGH DITF thru the Department of Health (DOH) and the report shall be discussed with the family thru our DOH Regional Offices.

Confidentiality:

All information gained from a hospital autopsy is confidential. All medical and autopsy information is communicated only between treating doctors, pathologists and other authorized health professionals. Confidentiality will be applied to any resulting medical publication to ensure the deceased's identity is not revealed.

If you have further questions, you can ask the attending physician or the pathologist.

Handwritten signatures and initials in black ink, including a large 'H' with a checkmark, a 'W', and other illegible marks.

ANNEX H

PAHINTULOT PARA SA AUTOPSIYA NG MGA NABAKUNAHAN NG DENG VAXIA

PANGALAN NG NAMATAY/PASYENTE: (Unang Pangalan, Gitnang Pangalan, Apeyido)	PETSA NG KAPANGANAKAN: (Buwan/Araw/Taon)	PETSA/ORAS NG KAMATAYAN: (Buwan/Araw/Taon) (12-hr format)
PANGALAN AT TITULO NG DOKTOR NA MAGSASAGAWA NG AUTOPSIYA:		BILANG NG LISENSYA:
PANGALAN NG PASILIDAD KUNG SAAN ISASAGAWA ANG AUTOPSIYA:		

Basahin muna ang nasa likod bago ito punan.

Ako, (Buong Pangalan) _____ na (ayon sa karapatang legal) [lagyan ng tsek ang alin mang naaangkop] magulang kapatid (18 taong gulang pataas) lolo/lola tagapangalaga (sa panahon ng pagkamatay) ng namatay, na binigyang-karapatan ng batas na magpasya sa pagsasaayos ng mga labi, ay pinahihintulutan ang patologo ng (Katuwang na Ospital ng Kagawaran ng Kalusugan/ DOH Autopsy Team) na magsagawa ng autopsiya sa katawan ng namatay.

Ipinahahayag ko sa abot ng aking kaalaman na wala akong nalalamang may higit na legal na karapatan kaysa sa akin na tatanggi sa pagsasagawa ng autopsiya.

Kung higit sa isang tao ang may legal na karapatan sa pagbibigay-pahintulot sa pagsasagawa ng autopsiya, sino man sa kanila ay maaaring magbigay ng pahintulot maliban na lamang kung may isang may katulad na karapatan ang maghahain ng pagtanggap sa doktor, medical eksaminer o hukom sa isang regular na hukuman. Kung may pagtanggap inihain, ang pahintulot ay maaari lamang maibigay ng mayorya ng mga taong may katulad na karapatan. Isang halimbawa nito ay ang mga anak na nasa hustong gulang.

Sa paglagda, pinahihintulutan ko ang pagkuha, eksaminasyon, at pagpapanatili ng mga *organ*, tisyu, kagamitang ipinlanta, at mga likidong nakikita ng patologo bilang kapaki-pakinabang sa imbestigasyon upang lubos na maunawaan ang sanhi ng pagkamatay at ang mga epekto ng panggagamot, para sa mga layuning dayagnostiko, pang-edukasyon at pananaliksik.

Pumapayag ako sa pagkuha ng mga litrato at anumang uri ng dokumentasyon bilang bahagi ng proseso ng otopsiya sa kondisyon na ang nasawi ay hindi makikilala sa kanyang pangalan, mukha, o anumang katangiang pisikal. Nauunawaan ko na ang mga litrato at anumang uri ng dokumentasyon kinuha ay hindi isasapubliko o gagamitin sa ibang layunin malibas sa nakasaad.

Nauunawaan kong kinakailangan ang pagpapadala ng mga maliliit na piraso ng tisyu (halimbawang dayagnostiko) para sa eksaminasyon sa laboratoryo. Mahalaga ito sa pagkakaroon ng buo at impormatibong autopsiya. Nauunawaan kong ang mga *organ* at mga tisyung hindi kailangan sa mga layuning dayagnostiko, pang-edukasyon, pampagpapataas ng kalidad, o

pampananaliksik ay ipadadala sa punerarya o kaya naman ay itatapon sa maayos na paraan. Sumasang-ayon din ako sa pamamaraan ng pagtapon ng mga materyales ayon sa patologo o ng ospital o ayon sa hinihingi ng batas.

Pinahihintulutan ko ang pag-gamit ng talaang medical at lahat ng angkop na impormasyon na nakalap mula sa ospital (o sa nakatalagang manggagamot) para sa layunin ng higit na pagsisyosat. Nauunawaan ko na mga talaang medical na ito ay gagamitin upang lubos na maunawaan ang sanhi ng pagkamatay at ang mga epekto ng panggagamot para sa mga layuning diyagnostiko, pang-edukasyon at pananaliksik.

Nauunawaan kong ano mang impormasyong dayagnostikong ibubunga ng autopsiya ay magiging bahagi ng talaang medical ng namatay at isusumite sa University of the Philippines – Philippine General Hospital Dengue Investigative Task Force (UP-PGH DITF) para sa ibayong pagsusuring pinahihintulutan ng batas.

Hindi kasama sa pahintulot na ito ang pagtatanggal ng mga *organ* at/o tisyu para sa pagta-transplant o mga katulad na gawain.

Nauunawaan kong maaari kong limitahan ang saklaw ng autopsiya at ang pag-iwan sa mga *organ*, tisyu, at mga devices. Nauunawaan ko na ano mang limitasyon ay maaaring makasama sa magiging dayagnostikong gamit ng autopsiya at makalilimita sa kapakinabangan ng autopsiya sa mga layuning pang-edukasyon, pagpapataas ng kalidad at pananaliksik.

Limitasyon sa autopsiya (pumili lamang ng isa)

- Wala. Pinahihintulutan ang isang **buong autopsiya**, nang may pagtatanggal, eksaminasyon at pagpapanatili ng mga materyal ayon sa pagpapasiya ng patologo para sa mga layuning itinakda sa itaas. Kaugnay nito ang pag-sangayon sa pamamaraan ng pagtapon ng materyales ayon sa patologo o ng ospital.

Limitahan ang autopsiya sa

- Parsyal na autopsiya (Thoracoabdominal Area)

_____ Eksaminasyong limitado sa atay lamang
_____ Eksaminasyong limitado sa atay, dibdib
_____ Eksaminasyong limitado sa atay at tiyan
_____ Eksaminasyong limitado sa atay, dibdib at tiyan
_____ Iba pa: (Tiyakin) _____

- Limitadong autopsiya: Pagkuha ng mga piraso ng tisyu sa pamamagitan ng *aspiration technique* sa isang tiyak na bahagi ng katawan. Pakisulat ang (mga) bahagi _____

Nabasa at naintindihan ko ang Autopsiya - Impormasyon para sa Pamilya (susunod na pahina)

pampananaliksik ay ipadadala sa punerarya o kaya naman ay itatapon sa maayos na paraan. Sumasang-ayon din ako sa pamamaraan ng pagtapon ng mga materyales ayon sa patologo o ng ospital o ayon sa hinihingi ng batas.

Pinahihintulutan ko ang pag-gamit ng talaang medical at lahat ng angkop na impormasyon na nakalap mula sa ospital (o sa nakatalagang manggagamot) para sa layunin ng higit na pagsisisyasat. Nauunawaan ko na mga talaang medical na ito ay gagamitin upang lubos na maunawaan ang sanhi ng pagkamatay at ang mga epekto ng panggagamot para sa mga layuning diyagnostiko, pang-edukasyon at pananaliksik.

Nauunawaan kong ano mang impormasyong dayagnostikong ibubunga ng autopsiya ay magiging bahagi ng talaang medical ng namatay at isusumite sa University of the Philippines – Philippine General Hospital Dengue Investigative Task Force (UP-PGH DITF) para sa ibayong pagsusuring pinahihintulutan ng batas.

Hindi kasama sa pahintulot na ito ang pagtatanggal ng mga *organ* at/o tisyu para sa pagta-transplant o mga katulad na gawain.

Nauunawaan kong maaari kong limitahan ang saklaw ng autopsiya at ang pag-iwan sa mga *organ*, tisyu, at mga devices. Nauunawaan ko na ano mang limitasyon ay maaaring makasama sa magiging dayagnostikong gamit ng autopsiya at makalilimita sa kapakinabangan ng autopsiya sa mga layuning pang-edukasyon, pagpapataas ng kalidad at pananaliksik.

Limitasyon sa autopsiya (pumili lamang ng isa)

- Wala. Pinahihintulutan ang isang **buong autopsiya**, nang may pagtatanggal, eksaminasyon at pagpapanatili ng mga materyal ayon sa pagpapasiya ng patologo para sa mga layuning itinakda sa itaas. Kaugnay nito ang pag-sangayon sa pamamaraan ng pagtapon ng materyales ayon sa patologo o ng ospital.

Limitahan ang autopsiya sa

- Parsyal na autopsiya (Thoracoabdominal Area)

_____ Eksaminasyong limitado sa atay lamang

_____ Eksaminasyong limitado sa atay, dibdib

_____ Eksaminasyong limitado sa atay at tiyan

_____ Eksaminasyong limitado sa atay, dibdib at tiyan

_____ Iba pa: (Tiyakin) _____

- Limitadong autopsiya: Pagkuha ng mga piraso ng tisyu sa pamamagitan ng *aspiration technique* sa isang tiyak na bahagi ng katawan. Pakisulat ang (mga) bahagi _____

Nabasa ko ang Autopsiya - Impormasyon para sa Pamilya (susunod na pahina)

Ipinabatid sa akin ang aking karapatang magkaroon ng doktor na pinili ko upang magmasid habang isinasagawa an autopsiya. (Itsek ang isang pagpipilian, at punan ang patlang kung kinakailangan):

- Pinawawalan ko ang aking karapatang magkaroon ng doktor na pinili ko upang magmasid habang isinasagawa ang autopsiya
- May doktor akong pinili upang magmasid habang isinasagawa ang autopsiya, siya ay si:

Buong Pangalan at Bilang ng Lisensya ng Doktor

Binigyan ako ng pagkakataong magtanong tungkol sa saklaw at layunin ng autopsiya.

**NAGBIBIGAY NG PAHINTUHOT
(PINAKAMALAPIT NA KAMAGANAK):**

Lagda: _____
Buong Pangalan: _____
Petsa (Buwan/Araw/Taon): _____

**IPINALIWANAG NI (AUTOPSY
TEAM):**

Lagda ng Saksi: _____
Pangalan at Posisyon: _____
Petsa (Buwan/Araw/Taon): _____

SAKSI:

Lagda ng Saksi: _____
Pangalan at Posisyon: _____
Petsa (Buwan/Araw/Taon): _____

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AUTOPSIYA – IMPORMASYON PARA SA PAMILYA

Ano ang autopsiya?

Isang doktor na may epesyalisasyon sa patolohiya (isang patologo) ay magsasagawa ng eksaminasyon ng isang bangkay upang matukoy ang sanhi ng kamatayan o ang mga katangian at saklaw ng mga pagbabagong dulot ng sakit. Kabilang dito ang panlabas at panloob na eksaminasyon ng bangkay at ng mga *organ* nito at sinasamahan ng mikroskopikong eksaminasyon kung kinakailangan.

Bakit ito isinasagawa?

Maaaring kumpirmahin o tukuyin ng autopsiya ang sanhi ng kamatayan, at tukuyin ang katangian at saklaw ng anumang sakit. Nakatutulong din itong maunawaan ang sakit ng namatay at sanhi ng kamatayan nito. Makapagbibigay ito ng impormasyong maaaring maging makabuluhan sa kalusugan mo o ng mga kamag-anak mo.

Pangkalahatang Impormasyon

- ❖ Maaari kang magpasiya kung ang namatay ay magkakaroon ng buo o ng limitadong autopsiya. Mahalagang maunawaan mo at maging komportable ka sa mga bagay kung saan hinihingi ang iyong pahintulot.
- ❖ Sa isang buong autopsiya, ang isang patologo ay nagsasagawa ng isang panlabas at panloob na eksaminasyon ng katawan. Upang maganap ito, ang mga laman-loob ay tinatanggal mula sa dibdib, tiyan at ulo at saka ineeksamen.
- ❖ Sa isang limitadong autopsiya, ang eksaminasyon ay nasa isang tiyak na bahagi o *organ* lamang na sinang-ayunan mong maeksamen. Gayunpaman, posibleng hindi maibigay ng isang limitadong autopsiya sa ospital ang lahat ng impormasyong kailangan sa pagtukoy ng sanhi o anumang nakapag-ambag sa kamatayan.
- ❖ Ang pagkuha at pag-iingat ng mga diagnostic sample ay karaniwang bahagi ng karamihan sa mga autopsiya. Ang mga sample na ito ay maaaring suriin ng isang patologo gamit ang isang mikroskopyo.
- ❖ Karamihan sa mga *organ a tisyu ay ibinabalik sa katawan pagkatapos ng isang autopsiya sa ospital maliban* na lamang kung ikaw ay nagbigay ng tiyak na pahintulot ng pag-iingat ng mga ito para sa ibayong eksaminasyon. May mga kalagayang medikal (katulad ng sakit sa utak) kung saan kakailanganin ang pag-iingat sa buong *organ*. Ang pagbibigay ng pahintulot sa patologo sa usaping ito ay makapagbubunga ng pinakamahusay na posibleng impormasyon sa huling ulat ng autopsiya.
- ❖ Sa pagtatapos ng eksaminasyon, ang mga *organ* at ano mang sample na mananatili ay:
 - tamang pamamaraan ng pagtapon ng ospital, o
 - kung iyong hihingin ay ibibigay sa isang tagapamahala ng punerarya o kremasyon sa isang tukoy na petsa, (maaaring magdulot ng karagdagang gastusin sa pamilya),
o
 - Kung iyong hihingin, ang lahat ng sample ay ibabalik sa katawan bago ang burol, (maaari ding makaragdag sa gastusin ng pamilya).

- ❖ Maaaring magbigay ng pahintulot sa pagbibigay ng mga diagnostic sample at/o pagkuha ng karagdagang tisyu para sa mga layuning pampananaliksik, pagtuturo at paggamit sa laboratoryo.

Ano ang mangyayari pagkatapos ng autopsiya?

Ang mga *organ* ay ibinabalik sa katawan at ang katawan ay isinasara nang may ibayong pag-iingat at paggalang upang maging maayos pa ring tingnan pagkatapos ng autopsiya sa ospital.

Kakailanganin bang ilipat ang petsa ng burol dahil dito?

Maapektuhan lamang ang petsa ng burol kung magpasiya kang ibalik sa katawan lahat ng diagnostic sample bago ang burol.

Paano malalaman ng pamilya ang resulta ng autopsiya?

Kukumpletuhin ng patologo ang detalyadong ulat ng autopsiya. Ipadadala ito sa UP-PGH DITF sa tulong ng Department of Health (DOH). Ang DOH Regional Offices ang siyang nakatalagang magtalakay ng resulta sa pamilya.

Pagiging Kompidensyal:

Lahat ng impormasyong makukuha sa isang autopsiya sa ospital ay kompidensyal. Lahat ng impormasyong medikal at mula sa autopsiya ay nasa mga doktor na naglapat ng atensyong medikal, patologo at iba pang awtorisadong health professional lamang. Ilalapat ang ganitong pag-iingat ng impormasyon sa anumang medikal na lathalain upang matiyak na hindi mabubunyag ang pagkakakilanlan ng namatay.

Kung may mga karagdagang katanungan, maaaring magtanong sa doktor na naglapat ng atensyong medikal o sa patologo.